

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D6.2: Technical description of the preliminary BlueBird Supportive Platform

WP6 – Supportive IT platform

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Contributors:

Document Section	Author(s)	Reviewer(s)
Table of Content	Gerard Laguna (CIMNE)	Jerson A. Pinzon (BPIE) Judith Kockat (BPIE)
I., II., V	Gerard Laguna (CIMNE) Núria Salvador (CIMNE) Jordi Carbonell (CIMNE)	Jerson A. Pinzon (BPIE) Judith Kockat (BPIE)
III . BlueBird repository	Eduardo Vendrell del Río (INETUM), Kevin Herrera Canate (INETUM)	Jerson A. Pinzon (BPIE) Judith Kockat (BPIE)
IV.	Baptiste Thiran (KARNO) Jordi Cipriano (CIMNE) Marcin Adamski (PSNC) Tomasz Ciesielczyk (PSNC) Niklas Friedel (ENLION) Jorit Körber (EWH)	Jerson A. Pinzon (BPIE) Judith Kockat (BPIE)
IV.3 (30/03)	François Bordes (WeSmart)	Gerard Laguna (CIMNE) Josep Mayos (CIMNE)

Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to outline the developments related to the implementation of services at the pilot sites. This implementation follows the reference architecture detailed in deliverable 6.1, titled “Privacy- and Security-by-Design Microservice Reference Architecture.” Since many of the pilot sites already have their own IT architectures, the proposed framework aims to facilitate the deployment of BlueBird services by reusing as many components as possible. This approach means that they can utilise existing components of their architecture and identify additional elements needed to meet the requirements for deploying BlueBird services. This approach helps with implementation, maintains the service after the project ends, and makes it easy to replicate at other sites.

Together with the implementation, the data standardisation and common data model are presented, based on the BIGG Ontology. Using an ontology when working with multiple data sources provides a shared conceptual model that standardises how data is interpreted across different systems. It helps resolve semantic differences between datasets by mapping various schemas and terms to a common vocabulary. Therefore, using an ontology improves interoperability and enables integrated querying across diverse sources.

Finally, this deliverable also presents the BlueBird repository, the GitHub repository where all components from the BlueBird project are uploaded, shared among partners, and made publicly available for replication purposes.

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Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
API	Application programming interface
BC	Business case
BMS	Building Management Systems
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DSO	Distribution System Operators
DT	Digital Twin
EV	Electric Vehicle
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HVAC	Heating, Ventilating and Air Conditioning
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PV	Photovoltaics
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SAREF	Smart Applications REference Ontology
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to outline the developments related to the implementation of services at the pilot sites. This implementation follows the reference architecture detailed in Deliverable 6.1, titled “Privacy- and Security-by-Design Microservice Reference Architecture.” Since many of the pilot sites already operate their own established IT infrastructures, the proposed framework is designed to support the deployment of BlueBird services while maximising the reuse of existing components. Rather than requiring a complete redesign of current systems, the framework enables each pilot site to integrate BlueBird services within their current architectures by identifying which components can be reused and which additional elements are required to satisfy the technical and operational requirements of the platform.

This approach not only simplifies the implementation process but also contributes to the long-term sustainability of the deployed services. By building on existing infrastructures, pilot sites are better positioned to maintain and operate the services beyond the duration of the project. Furthermore, this strategy promotes scalability and reproducibility, as other organisations can more easily replicate the implementation by adapting the framework to their own infrastructures while following the same architectural principles.

In addition to the implementation aspects, this document presents the approach adopted for data standardisation and the definition of a common data model, which is based on the BIGG Ontology. When working with multiple data sources originating from different systems and organisations, semantic inconsistencies often arise due to differences in data structures, naming conventions, and conceptual interpretations. The use of an ontology addresses these challenges by providing a shared conceptual model that standardises how data is represented and interpreted across systems. An ontology is a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualisation of a domain, defining its entities, relationships, and rules in a structured and machine-interpretable way. By mapping heterogeneous schemas and terminologies to a common vocabulary, the ontology facilitates semantic alignment between datasets. As a result, it improves interoperability between systems, enables integrated querying across heterogeneous data sources, and supports more consistent data exchange and analysis within the BlueBird ecosystem.

Finally, this deliverable also introduces the BlueBird repository, which serves as the central GitHub repository for the project. This repository hosts the different software components developed within the BlueBird project, allowing partners to access, share, and collaboratively maintain the project’s codebase. Beyond supporting internal collaboration, the repository also plays an important role in ensuring transparency and reproducibility. By making the developed components publicly available, it enables external stakeholders and organisations to review, reuse, and replicate the solutions developed within the project, thereby facilitating the broader adoption and long-term impact of the BlueBird framework.

II. COMMON DATA MODEL

The common data model is extracted from an ontology. The ontology is a key element that ensures the data model follows established data organisation standards, enabling interoperability with other databases and simplifying data integration. The ontology used is an evolution of the ontology developed in the European H2020 BIGG project. This ontology is open source and publicly available on GitHub: <https://github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/biggonontology>.

Initially, the ontology contained the necessary definitions to identify buildings, their regions, the energy-efficiency measures applied within them, and their types of energy consumption and associated costs. To incorporate the data required for the BlueBird project, several elements have been defined or redefined: the link that connects users when forming an energy community, the relative positions of spaces to consider multi-zone heating or cooling, the different tariffs and use market information, and the integration of capacity market data. Different elements present in the BlueBird pilots as heat pumps, water pumps, space heating and cooling elements and DHW were already considered.

These modifications have been carried out based on existing ontologies (CORE, SAREF, GEOESP, OWL, TIME, BIMERR, and FOAF) to ensure that the newly introduced fields remain aligned with them and maintain interoperability. For example, the adhesion of BIMERR was required in order to consider the multi-zone heating or cooling. The information on space collindance is present in the BIM information of the buildings, and to be able to systematically collect this information, this ontology was incorporated.

II.1. Ontology description

The BIGG Ontology is an open-source initiative that provides a standardised schema for describing, characterising, and analysing buildings and urban areas. The ontology supports urban planning, building management, and sustainable development by establishing a shared vocabulary for researchers and practitioners. This common language facilitates the integration and exchange of information across the urban development domain.

In addition, the ontology provides a framework for defining measurements and KPIs, enabling accurate assessment and comparison of building and urban area performance. The repository documents the ongoing development of the ontology and provides essential resources to support its implementation and practical use.

Figure 1. General ontology schema with references to the coupled ontologies.

Figure 2. Measurement representation with references to the coupled ontologies.

The ontology represents information using the Terse RDF Triple Language (Turtle). It is constructed with the Web Ontology Language (OWL), which is derived from the Resource Description Framework (RDF) standard defined by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and is typically expressed in XML. This method provides a robust and standardised framework for representing, structuring, and exchanging semantic data within the ontology. It ensures interoperability and consistency across systems that utilise or integrate with the model.

II.1.1. Ontology key components

The ontology is organised into five main components:

- Systems:** This component describes and analyses the various systems, sensors, devices, and weather stations found within buildings and urban areas. It covers their functions, interconnections, and performance. By modelling these elements and their relationships, the ontology facilitates efficient system operation, proper maintenance, and effective integration among different technological components. Ultimately, this contributes to improved building performance, reliability, and operational efficiency.

Figure 3. Diagram of the fields defining building and urban systems.

- Geospatial:** This component captures and represents the spatial characteristics and geographic information related to buildings and urban areas. It supports urban planning processes, optimal land use, site selection, and environmental impact assessments. By organising geospatial information in a standardised manner, the ontology enables informed decision-making and more efficient spatial management.

Figure 4. Diagram of the fields defining spatial characteristics and geographic information of buildings and urban areas.

- Measurements:** This component catalogues and standardises the various devices and sensors used in buildings and urban environments for data collection and monitoring. These devices include meters, thermostats, smart appliances, and sensors that measure variables such as temperature, humidity, occupancy, and energy consumption. By standardising these devices and their associated data, we ensure consistent and accurate data acquisition across different environments. This process supports reliable monitoring, data collection, analysis, and informed decision-making.

Figure 5. Diagram of the fields used to define and identify data obtained from measurements.

- Agents:** This component identifies and classifies the various actors and entities involved in the lifecycle of buildings and urban areas. These can include owners, occupants, operators, service providers, and other stakeholders. By organising information about these agents, the ontology enhances coordination, regulatory compliance, and collaboration among stakeholders, ultimately leading to more efficient and cohesive management of urban environments.

Figure 6. Diagram of the fields identifying the different agents and entities involved in building management.

- Temporal:** This component addresses time-related aspects such as the synchronisation of events, lifecycle phases of systems and components, and historical data associated with buildings and urban areas. Incorporating temporal information enables time-based analysis and planning, supports forecasting of future needs and allows the evaluation of long-term trends.

Figure 7. Diagram of the fields used to represent temporal information.

II.2. Data Model

Creating a data model is essential because it establishes a clear and structured framework that facilitates the understanding and management of information. Such a model helps identify relationships among entities, optimise database performance, and ensure data consistency and integrity. Additionally, it clarifies the system's specific requirements, simplifying collaboration between technical and functional teams.

A well-designed data model reduces errors, improves scalability, and simplifies long-term maintenance, providing a solid foundation for both system development and data analysis. The data model is particularly important for complex projects like BlueBird, which considers a wide variety of buildings and assets. The pilot portfolio includes residential households, tertiary buildings, hotels, and industrial systems such as waterworks and grid infrastructure. Managing these smart buildings and systems, which involve multiple data sources and interconnected subsystems, requires an integrated and consistent representation.

In this context, data harmonisation is a critical process for integrating information from diverse sources in a consistent and reliable manner. Data from different systems often have discrepancies in values, formats, and quality, hindering their usefulness for analysis or decision-making. For example, in the cadastre of a building or a building space, it can have different areas depending on whether it's considered the usable area, the full space area, or whether it also includes the exterior areas like balconies. Harmonisation addresses these inconsistencies by standardising formats and defining priority rules to determine which sources prevail in the event of conflicts. It also enables combining redundant data to produce unified metrics, such as total energy consumption for a building.

This process not only improves data quality but also enhances scalability, as new data sources can be incorporated without requiring a complete system restructuring. Ultimately, data harmonisation ensures

that database users can rely on the available information, maximising the value that can be extracted from data for decision-making, reporting, and the application of advanced analytics or automated processes.

II.2.1. Process for Creating the Graph Data Model in Neo4j

In the data model development, the following steps were iteratively followed until reaching the current version. The main steps in creating the graph data model in Neo4j are described below:

1. **Define Nodes:** Identify the primary entities in the domain (e.g., Heritage, Spaces, Objects) and their relevant properties.
2. **Define Relationships:** Establish how nodes are connected by defining relationship types (e.g., *geosp_sfContains*, *bigg_hasFeature*, *s4syst_hasSubSystem*) and their associated properties.
3. **Hierarchies and Dependencies:** Organise nodes into hierarchies or networks to reflect containment, lineage, or functional dependencies.
4. **Optimise Properties:** Assign meaningful attributes to nodes and relationships to capture domain-specific data (e.g., frequency and hash identifiers in SAREF Measurement nodes).
5. **Align with Ontologies:** Apply existing standards to ensure interoperability and maintain consistent semantics across the model.
6. **Test Cypher Queries:** Design and execute queries to verify that the model meets project requirements, including efficient retrieval of complex relationships.
7. **Iterate and Refine:** Continuously adjust the model using real data and practical use cases to improve effectiveness, scalability, and overall performance.

II.2.2. Main Entities and Relationships of the Data Model

The following section outlines the key components that structure the data model and their interactions. It identifies the primary entities (or nodes) and the relationships that connect them, capturing hierarchies, dependencies, and properties to ensure a coherent representation of the domain required for the project.

For clarity and functionality, the nodes in the data model can be categorised into three main domains:

1. **Georeferenced Nodes:** This category includes entities such as Heritage Assets, Spaces, and Municipalities, which define physical locations or spatial hierarchies within the system. These nodes serve as the geographic foundation of the model, linking assets and properties to their respective locations.
2. **Static Descriptive Nodes:** These nodes provide additional information about georeferenced nodes, including physical characteristics, uses, cadastral plots, addresses, and contractual details. This domain encapsulates static properties that do not change frequently but are essential for fully describing each entity.
3. **Connected Systems Nodes:** This category represents the technical infrastructure associated with heritage assets and spaces, including monitoring and control systems, IoT devices, and various physical systems (such as electric, water, and gas). This domain captures interactions between systems and spaces, facilitating real-time data analysis, resource management, and operational monitoring.

II.2.3. Georeferenced Nodes: Patrimony, Its Contents, and Containers

The main focus of the project is Patrimony (*bigg_Patrimony*), which is defined as a heritage asset. This definition extends beyond individual buildings to include entities comprising multiple buildings, larger structures, or various types of infrastructure. This broader interpretation of Patrimony enables the model to encompass any structure or set of elements under heritage management.

Patrimony nodes, along with their static properties and characteristics, are primarily created and maintained using data from the cadastre database. These nodes serve as the main source of detailed information, including essential descriptions and attributes.

Patrimony nodes are part of higher-level geolocated entities, such as neighbourhoods, municipalities, provinces, regions, or states. These geographic entities are initially sourced from databases such as cadastres, which provide location information (e.g., municipality and province). The data is then mapped to the *GeoNames* ontology, standardising entries to avoid typographical errors and facilitating data integration from multiple sources. This process also establishes additional relationships, such as the administrative hierarchy of municipalities within provinces, regions, and states.

Patrimony can include other georeferenced entities, such as Spaces or Zones (*bigg_BuildingSpaces*). These spaces can be recursively subdivided into smaller areas, creating a hierarchical “tree” structure that reflects the internal organisation of the heritage asset.

Spaces can also contain physical Objects (*bigg_BuildingObjects*), which include installations, equipment, and devices. These objects are categorised into different classes represented by the *bee_AssetLine* entity, which classifies them according to their functionality or specific technical characteristics.

Both Spaces and Objects are linked to entities that describe additional features beyond their inherent properties. For instance, *bee_SpaceFeatures* is associated with Spaces, while *bee_AssetFeatures* is linked to Objects. These entities can also connect to Work Orders (*bigg_WorkOrders*), which manage maintenance tasks or interventions.

Work Orders may include additional attributes (*bee_WorkOrderFeatures*) and belong to a defined category (*bee_WorkOrderLine*). They are further classified by service type (*bee_ServiceType*), issue type (*bee_IssueType*), or maintenance type (*bee_MaintenanceType*). To ensure effective management, Work Orders are linked to status log nodes (*bee_StatusLog*), which record the history and current status of each order.

Figure 8. Representation of the Relationship Between Building Spaces, Objects, and Work Orders.

Data related to Spaces, Objects, Work Orders, and their properties and characteristics is primarily created and updated using information from the cadastre database. This database can be linked with several public local indicators, such as economic or demographic studies. These indicators could provide valuable insights for comprehensive heritage analysis, facilitating informed decision-making.

Figure 9. Representation of the Relationship Between Patrimony and its Indicators.

II.2.4. Patrimony Static characteristics

Patrimony nodes consist of connected nodes that provide additional static descriptive information beyond the direct properties stored within the Patrimony node itself. This information is primarily sourced from the cadastral database. These static feature nodes may be associated not only with patrimony but also with other nodes contained within it (such as Spaces and Objects) or with nodes that encompass it (such as Municipalities). However, for the purposes of this project, these data are exclusively used to enrich the Patrimony nodes.

The most relevant static characteristics associated with patrimony include:

- Organisation (*schema:Organisation* → *bigg:isManagedBy*): This represents the organisations or sub-organisations responsible for managing the patrimony.
- Use Type (*bee:UseType* → *gn:featureCode*): This classifies the functional use of the patrimony, standardised according to the BIGG typologies that categorise its purpose or operational role.
- Area (*saref:Measurement* → *geosp:hasArea*): This defines the total surface area of the building or element associated with the patrimony.
- Cadastral Data (*bigg:CadastralParcel* and *bigg:Building* → *geosp:sfContains*): This represents the cadastral parcel associated with the patrimony, which may include one or more cadastral references.
- Address (*vcard:Address* → *vcard:hasAddress*): This provides the official address of the building, including details such as street name and number.
- Contract (*bigg:Contract* → *bigg:hasContract*): These nodes represent contracts associated with the patrimony, such as maintenance contracts. These contract nodes may also be linked to:
 - Company (*bigg:Company* → *bigg:hasCompany*): This identifies the company responsible for or associated with the contract.
 - MEC Classification (*bee:MEC* → *bee:hasMEC*): This is a classification or grouping of contracts based on their typology.
- Legal Status (*bigg:LegalStatus* → *bigg:hasLegalStatus*): This defines the legal status of the patrimony, such as ownership, lease, assignment, or usufruct.

Figure 10. Patrimony static characteristics representation.

II.2.5. System

In this project, Systems (*s4syst:System*) are defined as the technical infrastructure that supports and manages various functionalities within a property or space. These systems include physical devices, subsystems, and networks designed to monitor and control data, such as energy consumption, environmental conditions, and operational control systems. They play a key role in connecting devices and ensuring the effective functioning of the data infrastructure.

Systems may comprise different subsystems and devices (*saref:Device*). A device is defined as a physical or virtual element capable of collecting, processing, transmitting, or acting upon data within a system. These devices are fundamental components for monitoring and controlling system operations, enabling data acquisition, automation, and the management of building infrastructure.

II.2.5.a. Relation between systems and BuildingObject

In this data model, a clear distinction is made between physical assets or elements located within building spaces (primarily sourced from cadastre) and active building systems (typically originating from electrical systems or other operational platforms such as BMS).

- **Physical Assets or Elements:** These are items that are physically present within a specific area of the building. Their spatial relationship with the building space is represented by the link *geosp:sfContains*, indicating that the asset is contained within that particular space.
- **Active Systems:** These systems provide services to either the entire building or specific areas within it. Their relationship to spaces is represented through deployment nodes (*ssn:Deployment*). The link *ssn:isDeployedAtSpace* indicates the location where the system operates or provides its services.

Figure 11. System and BuildingObject relation.

In some cases, these physical assets may correspond directly to active systems. When this occurs, they are connected to the corresponding System node (*s4syst:System*) via the *owl:sameAs* relationship, indicating that both nodes refer to the same physical entity, represented in different data sources or perspectives within the model.

II.2.5.b. Relationship Between Harmonised Measurements of Building Systems (BuildingSystems) and Data Collection Systems (MonitoringAndControl)

In this model, two main categories of systems are distinguished, each associated with different types of data:

- Building Systems (BuildingSystems): These systems contain harmonised data organised into a single time series, tailored to the client’s preferences. The harmonisation process prioritises the most reliable or relevant data sources, ensuring a consistent, unified representation of measured parameters, such as the building's total electricity consumption.
- Monitoring and Control Systems (MonitoringAndControl): These systems handle raw data obtained directly from multiple sources, such as BACnet, Modbus, or Datadis platforms. This data is not processed or normalised, which may result in variations in quality, frequency, and format, depending on the originating system.

Figure 12. Relationship Between Harmonised Measurements of Building Systems and Data Collection Systems.

II.2.5.c. Measurement harmonisation

When multiple sources measure the same parameter, such as a building's total electricity consumption, which may be recorded via DATADIS, Modbus, or BACnet, the data are linked to a central, harmonised measurement node. This connection is represented using *owl:sameAs*, which links:

- Raw measurements (*saref:Measurement*) from different sources associated with devices belonging to Monitoring and Control systems (*MonitoringAndControl*).

- The harmonised measurement node, which is part of the Building Systems (*BuildingSystems*).

The harmonisation process offers several advantages:

- **Avoiding Redundancies:** Multiple measurements of the same parameter are unified into a single reference record.
- **Prioritising Sources:** The most reliable data source is selected based on criteria defined by the user. The process for prioritising sources is detailed in the time-series harmonisation procedure.
- **Simplifying Analysis:** A clean and consistent time series is generated, which facilitates monitoring, management, and analysis of key building performance parameters.

II.2.5.d. Device Properties and Measurement Units

Each device measures a specific property, referred to as *saref:Property*, which may include variables such as temperature, energy consumption, or humidity. These properties represent the physical or operational aspects that the device is intended to monitor within a given system.

Each property is associated with a unit of measurement, denoted as *qudt:Unit*, such as degrees Celsius (°C) or kilowatts (kW). This relationship is defined by the link *saref:isMeasuredIn*, which connects the measured property to its corresponding unit.

This framework ensures that all measurements recorded within the system are semantically defined and standardised. As a result, it enables consistent interpretation, comparison, and analysis of data across different devices, systems, and data sources.

II.2.5.e. Measurements Generated by Devices

Devices generate measurements through the relationship *saref:makesMeasurement*, which typically links the device to Measurement nodes (*saref:Measurement*). These nodes record the device's actual readings. The measurements may represent direct sensor readings or virtual measurements, created by combining other measurements or by applying calculations and transformations to existing data.

In addition to standard measurements, the model includes several specialised measurement types designed to support operational monitoring and analytical processes:

- **Expected Measurement (*bigg:ExpectedMeasurement*):** This represents a predicted or planned measurement generated by a system, often based on models, forecasts, or historical data.
- **Target Measurement (*bigg:TargetMeasurement*):** This defines a desired or goal value that a system or process aims to achieve, typically used in performance monitoring or optimisation strategies.
- **Limit Measurement (*bigg:LimitMeasurement*):** This establishes the maximum or minimum acceptable thresholds for a specific property.
- **Compliance Measurement (*bigg:ComplianceMeasurement*):** These measurements are used to verify whether the observed values comply with defined limits or targets, supporting validation processes and regulatory or operational checks.

These measurement categories enable the system not only to collect data but also to evaluate performance, enforce operational constraints, and support advanced analysis and decision-making.

II.2.5.f. Properties of Measurement Nodes

The design of the properties for nodes of type *saref:Measurement* is crucial for effectively managing data within the project's system. This structure allows measurements to be handled with high levels of detail, ensuring clear traceability through a hash identifier, information about measurement frequency, and, when applicable, the calculation formula (*bee_calculationFormula*) used to generate the measured value.

The main properties are described below:

- ***bigg_hash*:** This property represents a unique key, generated from the Base64-encoded URI, serving as the primary identifier of the measurement node. It links the Neo4j database to the time-

series database that stores the actual measurement records, ensuring traceability and consistency between the two systems.

- *bigg_measurementFrequency*: This property indicates the frequency at which measurements are collected, following the ISO 8601 duration format. The main frequencies used in the project include:
 - PT15M – Measurements collected every 15 minutes
 - P1D – Measurements collected daily
 - P1M – Measurements collected monthly
 - P1Y – Measurements collected yearly
- *bee_calculationFormula*: When present, this property defines the formula used to calculate the measurement value. It contains an encoded representation of the mathematical expression, allowing the calculation process used by the device or system to be clearly understood and reproduced. The formula structure supports several elements:
 - `<mh></mh>` – Measurement reference (Base64 Measurement URI): Contains the Base64-encoded URI of another *saref:Measurement* used as an input in the calculation. This method allows existing measurements within the system to be referenced and combined.
 - `<mo></mo>` – Mathematical operations: Defines the operations used to combine measurements, constants, or values. Supported operations include:
 - Addition (+)
 - Subtraction (-)
 - Multiplication (*)
 - Division (/)
 - `<mv></mv>` – Numeric values: Allows the inclusion of explicit numeric values within the formula, such as coefficients or adjustment factors.
 - `<mc></mc>` – Constants: Represents predefined constants in the system (e.g., specific energy constants, standard rates, or other fixed values required for calculations).
 - `<mq></mq>` – Base64-encoded Neo4j queries: Contains Cypher queries encoded in Base64, used to retrieve dynamic information from the Neo4j graph. For example, these queries may obtain related measurements, limit values, or other contextual data required for the calculation. Encoding these elements in Base64 ensures compatibility across systems and prevents transmission errors.
- URI: This property represents the unique identifier of the measurement, providing complete contextual information about the data point. It may include details such as the type of consumption (e.g., active energy), the associated device, and other contextual parameters. The URI can also be used to reference the measurement directly from other systems.

Together, these properties enable measurement nodes to support traceability, interoperability, calculation reproducibility, and integration with external time-series storage systems, forming a robust foundation for managing measurement data within the project's infrastructure.

II.2.6. Structure of Systems in the Project

In this project, systems (*s4syst:System*) play a fundamental role in managing and monitoring buildings. These systems can serve the entire building or specific areas within it, and they are linked to these areas via the *s4agri:isDeployedAtSpace* relationship, which uses deployment nodes (*ssn:Deployment*). This structure establishes a direct connection between the systems and the spaces where they are implemented. These systems may also feature a hierarchical substructure consisting of subsystems and devices, which represent their physical and functional implementations.

Monitoring and Control Systems (*bigg:MonitoringAndControl*) are primarily responsible for collecting and storing raw data records from various sources. They serve as an initial repository for data maintained in its original, unprocessed form, without any harmonisation or transformation. This methodology allows the data to be reused later according to the specific analytical or operational needs of the building.

Subsystems are organised based on the technologies or protocols used to collect the data. One example of this is the Weather subsystem, which gathers climatic and forecast data for each asset's location, including temperature, global horizontal solar radiation, and atmospheric pressure.

Each subsystem may include Associated Devices that are specifically responsible for capturing information accurately and in detail. These devices are critical for ensuring the precision and reliability of the data collected.

II.2.6.a. Structure of MonitoringAndControl Systems (*bigg:MonitoringAndControl*)

The main function of this system is to act as a central platform for collecting and storing raw building data. These data originate from multiple sources, which may include:

- Industrial communication protocols
- Energy analytics platforms
- Other specialised monitoring services

II.2.6.b. Building Systems

Building Systems (*bigg:BuildingSystem*) refer to the physical implementation of devices within a building's infrastructure. These systems organise devices in a harmonised and standardised structure, making it easier to interpret and utilise the collected data.

Key characteristics include:

- Unique Measurements and Source Prioritisation: Measurements recorded by devices are unified and harmonised. Data from different monitoring and control systems may be combined according to priority rules. For example, if three different sources measure the same parameter, a preferred source is chosen to ensure consistency and reliability.
- Types of Subsystems: Subsystems are classified based on their functional domains, including:
 - Consumption-related systems, such as electricity, gas, and water.
 - Management and control systems, which pertain to services like space heating, cooling, and domestic hot water (DHW).
- Associated Devices: Devices within these harmonised systems are responsible for efficient data acquisition, enabling accurate monitoring and supporting the optimisation of building operations.

II.2.6.c. Structure of Consumption Building Systems

The following section outlines the hierarchical structure of building consumption systems and their related subsystems. The electrical system serves as an example, though this structure can also apply to other resource systems.

- Electrical System (*bee:Electric, bigg:BuildingSystem*)
 - The main electrical system comprises the building's overall electrical infrastructure.
 - Deployment relationship: This system is deployed within a specific building or part of it and is connected to the spaces where it operates. The main system serves as the origin for several specialised subsystems:
 - 1) *bigg:Storage* (Energy Storage): Represents systems responsible for storing energy, typically through technologies such as batteries.
 - 2) *bigg:Generation* (Energy Generation): Includes systems that generate electrical energy, such as renewable energy installations or other generation sources.
 - 3) *bigg:GridSystem* (Electrical Grid): Represents the subsystem connecting the building's internal electrical infrastructure with the external power grid or supply points. Contains devices (*saref:Device*) that monitor connection points, such as meters or measurement instruments.

- 4) *bigg:ConsumptionSystem* (Energy Consumption): Represents the subsystem responsible for building energy consumption.
- Contains devices (*saref:Device*) monitoring the general consumption points of the building.
 - Includes specialised consumption subsystems. Examples include:
 - *bigg:Lighting*: Responsible for managing and monitoring energy consumption related to building lighting systems.
 - *bigg:HVAC*: Represents indoor climate control systems. It can be further subdivided into: *bigg:DHW*, *bigg:Heating*, *bigg:Cooling*, *bigg:Ventilation*.
 - *bigg:Appliances*: Includes electrical appliances such as washing machines, refrigerators, and other equipment.
 - *bigg:Refrigeration*: Subsystems dedicated to specific refrigeration systems.
 - *bigg:RechargePoint*: Systems responsible for electric vehicle charging infrastructure.

Overall, this hierarchical system structure allows the project to accurately represent building infrastructure, organise devices and measurements, and support advanced monitoring and energy management capabilities.

III. BLUEBIRD REPOSITORY

GitHub serves as the centralised repository for all code, configuration artefacts, and technical documentation developed in the project, providing a single access point and version control for all technology partners and pilot sites. It also serves the purpose of replicability, allowing any other organisation to replicate BlueBird's results.

The project's GitHub organisation (BlueBird-project) is available at <https://github.com/BlueBird-project>. It groups the different software components defined in the reference architecture, aligned with the functional modules described in this deliverable.

The repositories are open for reading and downloading, allowing cloning and reuse of the code without restrictions, both within and outside the consortium; therefore, partners are explicitly requested not to store sensitive or confidential information in the repositories.

III.1. Modular organisation in GitHub

The repository follows a module-based organisation that reflects the functional blocks of the BlueBird architecture, as defined in deliverable 6.1.

In practice, repositories are grouped into three main module categories:

- User interaction tools: include components oriented to end users, such as the graphical user interface (GUI), the recommendation engine, and gamification and quiz elements.
- Flexibility Manager: groups services related to forecasting, optimisation, and digital twin models that compute and exploit asset flexibility.
- Trading Manager: contains components for interaction with markets and system operators (for example, DSO interface, flexibility bidding optimisation, and knowledge extraction client).

GITHUB Organization

Figure 14. GitHub organisation, following the modules' structure approach

Each module may include both a generic implementation and pilot-specific adaptations, following a “pick-and-choose” approach that is consistent with the modular design of BlueBird.

The organisation in modules allows each pilot to select only the functionalities required to cover the use cases defined in deliverable 2.1, maximising reuse of common code and reducing ad hoc developments.

III.2. Use of the repository by the pilots

The technology partners in the consortium are responsible for developing, maintaining, and documenting the modules assigned to them, including deployment and integration guidelines for each demo site's local architecture.

Pilots access the GitHub organisation to download the released versions of each module (source code, container-ready Docker images, configuration templates, etc.) and integrate them into their infrastructures, following the procedures described in their documentation.

When the same module is adapted for several pilots, specific branches or subdirectories are used to separate configurations and extensions per business case, while keeping a shared code base.

This approach facilitates replicability across pilots and ensures traceability of each technical partner's contributions.

III.3. Access management and governance

Access to the BlueBird GitHub organisation is coordinated by INETUM, acting as the repository manager.

An up-to-date list of authorised users (by partner, role, and permission level) is maintained in the project SharePoint space. It serves as the single reference for creating, modifying, and revoking accounts.

Based on this list, INETUM configures teams and permissions in GitHub (e.g., read-only, developer, or maintainer access), ensuring each user is granted only the privileges required for their tasks.

This procedure guarantees centralised, auditable access management, while preserving the repository's open nature for code download and encouraging collaboration among all consortium members.

IV. BLUEBIRD INTEGRATION AND DEPLOYMENT AT DEMO SITES

IV.1. BC1 – Karno Residential buildings with geothermal and PV based heat grid

In the Karno pilot, several modules will be deployed. In the initial phase of the project, the focus has been primarily on defining the services and installing or adapting the necessary infrastructure.

IV.1.1. IT structure deployed

The BlueBird services in the Karno pilot will be hosted on Google Cloud Platform. The IoT architecture relies on Google Cloud services (BigQuery, Cloud Run). For the BlueBird specific needs, a containerised micro-service approach will be based on Docker and either Google Kubernetes Engine or Google Cloud Run, which aligns with the expected BlueBird deployment format.

Data is collected from two types of sources. Third-party data, specifically PV production data, is ingested via external API calls. Building-level data is acquired through an on-site Gateway-Control Box that aggregates data from both the electricity grid meter and the energy centre PLC, collecting all energy- and sensor-related data. The Control Box transmits data to the central ingestor layer via the MQTT protocol. Also, it receives control setpoints generated by the BlueBird optimisation layer and relays them to the PLC for automated actuation.

Once ingested, data is processed through Cloud Run Jobs, which handle API calls for both third-party and gateway data streams, as well as the generation and dispatch of control setpoints back to the on-site PLC. All processed data will be stored in Google BigQuery, which serves as the central long-term storage layer for the pilot.

The BlueBird analytics services will be connected to BigQuery and organised into three functional blocks: the Flexibility Manager, which arbitrates and sends the optimisation outputs to the system; the Digital Twin, which contains the dynamics of the system to foresee the system response; and the Forecast module, which covers weather and market prices. Market price will be the market price signals retrieved from the electricity market. It is treated as a forecast input rather than a trading signal, as active market participation is outside the current scope. Outputs from the analytics layer, in particular, optimised control setpoints over the forecast horizon, will be fed back into the system to enable automated actuation on the physical assets.

Deploying the BlueBird components in their expected containerised form should not pose any significant integration issues, given the existing Cloud Run and Docker-compatible infrastructure.

Figure 15. BC1 deployed architecture integrating BlueBird services.

IV.1.2. Modules within the BC1 pilot

As illustrated in Figure 16, the Karno pilot implements a set of BlueBird services centred around two complementary strategies for unlocking energy flexibility. The central component is the Flexibility Manager, which integrates outputs from the Forecasting services and the Digital Twin simulation to generate optimised operational schedules.

In this business case, the digital twin models will represent the thermal and electrical behaviour of the assets connected to the district energy system. These models will enable estimation of available flexibility, thermal demand, and system response under varying operating conditions, supporting predictive control over the forecast horizon.

The Forecasting module will provide both weather-based and market-price forecasts to feed into the Flexibility Manager. Market price data is retrieved from the electricity market and incorporated as a forecast input to support cost-aware optimisation, as market participation via Trading Manager is outside the current scope.

The optimisation operates on two levels. At the technical level, the Flexibility Manager will generate optimised control setpoints, which are dispatched directly to the physical assets via the Building/Heat Grid Data Exchange Connectors, enabling automated load management across the district energy infrastructure. At the behavioural level, optimisation recommendations will be delivered to the User Interaction Tools, which include a User Communication component and a Gamification / Quizzes feature. These mechanisms aim to engage users through targeted recommendations and behavioural nudges. If acted upon, these user-side responses could further increase the overall flexibility yield achieved by the technical optimisation layer.

Figure 16. BC1 BlueBird services scheme.

IV.1.3. BC1 pilot asset communication

The Karno pilot will connect to the district energy system via on-site Gateway-Control Box. This gateway aggregates data from two sources: the electricity grid meter, providing real-time monitoring of electrical consumption and production at the site level, and the PLC, which interfaces with the thermal and mechanical systems of the energy infrastructure. The Control Box also receives control setpoints generated by the BlueBird optimisation layer and relays them to the PLC, enabling closed-loop automated actuation.

In addition to building-level data, third-party PV data will be integrated via an external API, providing solar production measurements and forecasts that feed into both the Forecasting and Flexibility Manager modules.

All data streams will converge through the MQTT ingestor and be processed via Cloud Run Jobs before being stored in Google BigQuery. This centralised storage layer will then be accessed by the full suite of BlueBird analytics services, closing the loop from data acquisition to optimised control and user engagement.

IV.2. BC2 - PV self-consumption optimisation and occupant-driven flexibility of public buildings on the Iberian electricity trading markets

In the pilot from Metropolitan Area of Barcelona (AMB), several modules have been deployed. In the initial part of the project the focus has been the definition of the services, install infrastructure, collect and organise data.

IV.2.1. IT structure deployed

The BlueBird services in the AMB pilot are hosted in CIMNE’s servers. The IoT architecture is based on a Kubernetes microservice architecture. In this architecture, there is an ingestor module that receives data from APIs, MQTT, Bacnet and is prepared to be adaptable to new protocols, if needed.

Once data is ingested into the architecture, it is treated differently depending on whether it is static or time series data. If the received data is static, it is harmonised and stored in a Neo4j non-structured database. If the data received is from a time series, it is stored in HBASE in raw format and is also harmonised and stored in the InfluxDB database. In both cases, the harmonisation process consists of identifying the received data in the project data model and transforming it to the project standard storage format.

The BlueBird services are connected to both databases to have the necessary information to do all the analytics required. Results from this analysis are stored in the databases and then, if required, provided to the visual interfaces and sent the required signals to the external assets.

The architecture is deployed through Docker; therefore, the BlueBird components deployment in the expected containerised form should not pose any issues.

Figure 17. BC2 deployed architecture

IV.2.2. Modules within the BC2 pilot

At this pilot site, multiple actuation strategies are implemented to unlock building-level energy flexibility. As illustrated in Figure 18, the central component of the architecture is the Flexibility Manager, which integrates building and asset-level digital twins with forecasting services.

In this business case, the digital twin models represent the thermal behaviour of tertiary-sector buildings, including their heating, cooling, and mechanical ventilation systems. Additional models are implemented in the sports centre building for DHW production and for swimming pool heating. These physics-based and data-driven models enable predictive control by estimating thermal demand, comfort constraints, and system response under different operating scenarios.

The Flexibility Manager interacts with the Trading Manager to incorporate market signals into the optimisation process. In the current implementation, market interaction is limited to retrieving price signals from the Iberian electricity markets, specifically the day-ahead market and the three intraday sessions. These price inputs are used to generate cost-optimised operational schedules while respecting technical and comfort constraints. In future iterations, this module could be extended to offer flexibility services to the market actively.

Based on the optimisation results, combining Digital Twin outputs, forecasting data, and market signals, the resulting actuation profiles can be deployed either directly to the controlled assets for automated execution or delivered to User Interaction Tools, enabling supervised control or behavioural engagement mechanisms. The controlled assets in this business case include the heating and cooling systems of the participating buildings, as well as the swimming pool heating system and the DHW storage tanks at the sports centre.

In addition to automated control strategies, a behavioural (nudging) approach is implemented in one specific case related to electric vehicle charging. This mechanism aims to influence user charging patterns through targeted signals, complementing the technical flexibility strategies deployed at the system level.

Figure 18. BC2 BlueBird services scheme.

IV.2.3. BC2 pilot electric assets communication

This business case comprises 3 buildings that represent a large number of buildings in the Barcelona Metropolitan area. These buildings include an old town hall reconverted into a multi-purpose building with offices, a museum, and teaching rooms; a Sports Centre with a climatized pool; and a civic centre. Due to several factors, these buildings are in different deployment phases.

Multi-purpose building - Casa de la Vila de Montcada i Reixac

The pilot site consists of a multi-purpose municipal building located in Montcada i Reixac. The building is integrated with the BlueBird services (in CIMNE's servers) through a secure VPN connection established via a dedicated on-site gateway.

Through this connection, the BMS is remotely accessible for both data acquisition and supervisory control. Specifically, the system enables the collection of HVAC (climatisation) data and the monitoring and adjustment of temperature setpoints and operational status across the building's 33 climatized zones.

Data from the BMS is first acquired and stored locally in the gateway, which performs initial processing and validation. The data is then transmitted via the MQTT protocol to the central architecture that hosts the BlueBird services. This architecture supports data ingestion, storage, and further processing for monitoring, analytics, and optimisation purposes.

The building's digital twin has already been developed and made available in GitHub repository¹. Also collects market information data from the Trading Manager².

Sport centre – Illa esportiva Castellbisbal

The pilot site consists of a public sports centre located in the municipality of Castellbisbal. The objective at this site is to exploit the flexibility potential of the pool heating system and the DHW storage tanks, which are primarily used to supply hot water for the showers.

Historically, the building's thermal demand has been covered by a gas boiler. Between January and February 2026, additional equipment was installed to enhance operational flexibility and enable hybrid operation. This equipment includes a new HVAC system to complement the gas boiler for pool heating, as well as two electric resistance heaters integrated into the DHW storage tanks. These upgrades enable partial electrification of thermal demand and provide greater control over load shifting strategies.

In addition to the heating infrastructure, lighting systems have been installed to support testing of nudging strategies aimed at influencing user behaviour for the electric vehicle (EV) chargers connected to the facility. These interventions aim to assess how visual signals and behavioural cues can contribute to more efficient and flexible energy use patterns.

The contracted installation also includes a local data acquisition system connected to an on-site gateway. This gateway will aggregate operational data from the various systems and subsequently connect to the same backend services currently used for the Casa de la Vila building. At present, data integration has not yet been initiated, as the hardware installation and commissioning process are still ongoing.

¹ Montcada building digital twin:

<https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/dt/BlueBird-multizone-modelling/BC2%20-%20Montcada%20building>

² Trading Manager : <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/trading-manager>

Civic centre – Centre Cívic Virgínia Amposta

The pilot building is a civic centre in the municipality of Sant Vicenç dels Horts. The building houses municipal offices, meeting rooms, and spaces for cultural and community activities. It is equipped with an existing BMS. The primary objective at this site is to leverage the building's energy flexibility by implementing coordinated control of the HVAC and mechanical ventilation systems. Through optimised supervisory control strategies, the project aims to enable load shifting and demand side management while maintaining indoor comfort and air quality requirements.

The current BMS includes a web-based graphical user interface for monitoring purposes; however, this interface does not support remote or automated actuation. Data gathering and direct control are technically feasible through the BACnet communication protocol, which provides access to measurement points and control variables at the system level. Access to the BACnet network requires connection to the building's internal network infrastructure. However, this infrastructure is shared with the municipal town hall, creating cybersecurity and governance constraints. The municipal IT department has expressed concerns about granting external access to the network due to the absence of a zero-trust architecture in the municipal network. Discussions are ongoing with the municipal IT team to define a secure, compliant solution that enables communication with the measurement devices and remote operation of the HVAC and ventilation systems.

Once this connection issue is resolved, the data-gathering process can begin.

IV.3. BC3 – Tour & Taxis and Greenbizz sites: Mixed-use buildings and REN

The use cases developed in the WeSmart business case focus on providing user recommendations to empower users in knowledge-based energy consumption, with the aim of reducing their energy consumption cost. For these recommendations, knowledge from the electric market is needed, which will be provided through the Trading Manager. Additionally, a measurement campaign using smart plugs is being prepared to enable granular monitoring of individual appliance consumption within the energy community.

IV.3.1. IT structure deployed

The BlueBird services in the WeSmart pilot are integrated into a cloud-native serverless architecture. Unlike container-based deployments used in other pilots, the WeSmart platform operates on a fully managed infrastructure that does not rely on Docker or Kubernetes. Instead, backend logic is implemented through Supabase Edge Functions (Deno/TypeScript), which run in a serverless environment with automatic scaling and zero infrastructure management overhead.

Data is collected from the Distribution System Operator (Sibelga, Brussels DSO) via an authenticated API connection. Validated 15-minute interval meter data for both consumption and injection is retrieved monthly. At Greenbizz, additional real-time data is available from the battery system (50 kW / 120 kWh, managed by Octave) including State of Charge and power flows at 15-minute granularity.

All data is stored in a managed PostgreSQL database (Supabase) with Row Level Security (RLS) ensuring per-project data isolation. The database serves as the central storage layer for energy flows, participant data, economic parameters, and partner recommendations.

BlueBird components integrate with the WeSmart platform via a dedicated REST webhook endpoint (Partner Recommendations API). This API-first approach enables seamless integration without requiring local container deployment. The endpoint has been tested successfully with Inetum using Python-based API calls.

The WP3 optimisation model is being integrated through this same webhook mechanism, with optimisation results pushed as recommendations to the WeSmart platform.

Figure 19. BC3 Supportive IT platform for real time recommendation data workflow

IV.3.2. Modules within the BC3 pilot

As illustrated in Figure 19, the WeSmart pilot implements BlueBird services centred around user engagement through data-driven recommendations and community energy optimisation.

The central integration point is the Partner Recommendations API, which receives outputs from external BlueBird components (Flexibility Manager, forecasting services, Digital Twin) and delivers them in real-time to authenticated end-users via WebSocket (Supabase Realtime). Recommendations are categorised by type (EV charging, battery, heating, appliance, solar, grid) and action (suggestion, alert, automation), with configurable priority levels and time windows.

The platform supports the following BlueBird service modules:

- Forecasting (T3.1): Consumption prediction for residential participants (Tour & Taxis) and business participants (Greenbizz) based on 15-minute historical DSO data. The DTU forecasting model receives this data and generates predictions that feed into the Flexibility Manager.
- Flexibility Manager (T3.3) / Optimisation (T3.4): External optimisation algorithms push results via the webhook API. At Tour & Taxis, flexibility is limited to behavioural recommendations (no direct asset control). At Greenbizz, the battery system offers potential for technical flexibility, subject to coordination with Octave (battery operator).
- Digital Twin (T3.5): Building energy models can be fed with real consumption data retrieved from the Sibelga DSO API to simulate optimisation scenarios.
- User Interaction Tools (T4.3) / User Communication (T6.3): The WeSmart EMS dashboard displays real-time popup notifications for incoming recommendations with accept/dismiss actions. Missed messages are queued and shown on the user's next login. The platform also generates monthly energy reports comparing community vs. grid consumption, serving as the primary communication channel for financial and motivational incentives.
- DSO Communication (T5.1): Real-time data acquisition from Sibelga is operational. The DSO Interface testing (UC 3.4) is scoped for the Greenbizz site.
- Impact Analysis (T3.5): Energy bills analysis (UC 3.5) demonstrates reduced costs through community self-consumption. Monthly reports track community self-consumption rate, participant engagement, and grid dependency reduction.

IV.3.3. BC3 pilot asset communication

The WeSmart pilot connects to two types of data sources:

DSO data (Sibelga): Validated 15-minute consumption and injection data for all community members is retrieved via the Sibelga authenticated API. This data becomes available monthly for the previous month, ensuring accuracy and reliability. Additionally, day-after (D+1) non-validated data is available for the Greenbizz site, enabling near-real-time monitoring.

Battery data (Greenbizz): The 50 kW / 120 kWh battery operated by Octave provides real-time State of Charge (kWh) and power flow (kW) data at 15-minute intervals via the Octave API.

Smart plug data (planned): A one-month measurement campaign using smart plugs at participant premises is technically prepared and ready to launch. This will provide appliance-level consumption data to support flexibility assessment and recommendation calibration.

BlueBird component integration: External BlueBird services communicate with the WeSmart platform exclusively through the Partner Recommendations API:

- Endpoint: POST /functions/v1/receive-partner-recommendation.
- Authentication: Dual-layer — JWT Bearer token + Partner API Key (X-API-Key header).

- Rate limits: 100 requests/hour, 1,000/day per partner.
- Duplicate protection: Same-title recommendations within a 5-minute window are rejected.
- Real-time delivery: Recommendations are pushed to connected users via WebSocket within < 2 seconds

All communications use HTTPS/TLS 1.3 encryption. The platform is hosted in an EU datacenter (Supabase EU region) ensuring GDPR compliance and EU data residency.

IV.4. BC4 - ENEA Operator – Office Building

According to deliverable 6.1, the architecture proposed will be implemented in the pilot “ENEA Operator – Office Building.” The software components developed or used within the project, delivered in the form of modules or packages, will be installed on the ENEA infrastructure by engineers from PSNC.

Figure 20. BC4 BlueBird services scheme.

After installing sensors (thermostats) and Bluetooth gateways, the Home Assistant software platform will collect data and also receive actuation commands from the Flexibility Manager through the Building Data Exchange Connector. Home Assistant provides native integration with the sensors used in this pilot, enabling efficient communication and control of the devices. The collected data will be stored in a local PostgreSQL database. When required, selected data streams may be transmitted using the MQTT protocol to a supervisory system or through the dedicated Knowledge Engine client. In this context, the supervisory system should be understood as a BMS used by ENEA to consolidate information from both ENEA pilot installations.

The system will provide the following functionalities:

- configuration of temperature setpoints for each thermostat and real-time monitoring of temperature and humidity values,
- access to historical records of thermostat settings as well as temperature and humidity measurements,
- implementation of dedicated control algorithms for thermostat management depending on the time of day or longer time horizons; such algorithms will be proposed based on data analysis, including the use of digital twin models and forecasting services,
- generation of daily and long-term reports and the possibility to compare different time periods with respect to environmental parameters and system performance.

For security reasons, the system will not have direct connectivity to external networks or the public Internet. All software modules delivered as containerised components (Docker containers) will undergo a strict internal security audit within ENEA before deployment to the production environment. Access to the system components will be possible only from the internal ENEA network infrastructure.

Figure 21. BC4 system operation schematics with mockup.

IV.4.1. Software components used in the system

The pilot implementation will rely on the following software elements:

- Home Assistant: a local BMS-type platform responsible for managing sensors, collecting measurements, and executing automation logic,
- PostgreSQL database: used for persistent storage of sensor data and system events underneath the Home Assistant,
- Supervisory system (BMS): Dockerised higher-level system responsible for aggregating and visualising information from ENEA pilot installations.

Communication between system components will be based on:

- MQTT protocol: enables lightweight, efficient data exchange between sensors, gateways, and the supervisory system. In the target configuration, secured MQTT communication (e.g., TLS-based MQTT) will be implemented.
- Interaction with energy markets:
 - Knowledge Engine Smart Connector: communication based on the semantic technologies and ontology (e.g. SAREF)

According to the current assumptions, the system proposed in this pilot will not directly interact with energy markets. However, the architecture has been designed in a modular way, allowing for possible future integration with external energy market platforms or flexibility markets if such functionality is required in subsequent project stages.

IV.5. BC5 - PSNC & ENEA Operator – Grid Building

Similar to the first ENEA pilot, and in accordance with the assumptions described in deliverable 6.1, the architecture proposed will be implemented within the pilot “ENEA Operator – Grid Building.” The software components developed or adopted within the project, delivered as modules and software packages, will be installed on ENEA’s infrastructure by PSNC engineers.

Figure 22. BC5 BlueBird services scheme.

After the installation of the sensors (including thermostats and air-conditioning sensors) and communication gateways (WiFi/Bluetooth), operational data will be collected by the Home Assistant platform. In this pilot deployment, Home Assistant may act as a Flexibility Manager at the building level, enabling monitoring and control of environmental parameters within the facility. Home Assistant provides native integration with the sensors used in this pilot, which simplifies the process of data acquisition and device management.

All collected data will be stored in a local database (PostgreSQL) hosted within ENEA’s infrastructure. When required, selected datasets will be transmitted using the MQTT protocol to a higher-level supervisory system, understood as a BMS within ENEA, which will also act as a Flexibility Manager for the ENEA Grid buildings. This supervisory layer will enable aggregation and unified analysis of data originating from both ENEA pilot deployments and will be integrated with the knowledge engine.

The implemented system will provide the following functionalities:

- configuration of temperature setpoints on each thermostat, as well as real-time monitoring of temperature and humidity values,
- access to historical records of thermostat settings together with archived temperature and humidity measurements,
- implementation of advanced control algorithms for thermostats and air-conditioning systems based on time-dependent strategies (daily or longer time horizons). These strategies will be proposed after analysing collected data using digital twin techniques and forecasting services,

- the control algorithm/model may be implemented using a machine learning model trained offline on data gathered from the sensors deployed in the pilot environment,
- generation of daily and long-term analytical reports, including comparison of different time periods with respect to temperature profiles, environmental conditions, and energy usage patterns,
- integration with the Capacity Market through the BlueBird Trading Manager module, implemented using the Knowledge Engine software developed within the project.

For security reasons, the system will not maintain direct connectivity with the external Internet. All software modules will be delivered in containerised form (Docker containers) and, prior to deployment, will undergo a strict internal security audit conducted by ENEA. Access to system components will be limited exclusively to ENEA's internal network infrastructure.

Figure 23. BC4 system operation schematics with mockup.

IV.5.1. Software components used in the pilot

- Home Assistant: a local BMS-type platform responsible for sensor integration, monitoring, and control of building devices.
- PostgreSQL database: used for local data storage and historical data management.
- Supervisory system (BMS): an upper-layer system aggregating information from multiple ENEA pilots.

Communication between system components will be based on:

- MQTT protocol: with planned secure MQTT implementation in the final deployment,

- Knowledge Engine and Smart Connector: communication based on the semantic technologies and ontology (e.g. SAREF), enabling interaction with external market-related services.

According to the design assumptions, the system implemented in this pilot will interact with the energy market, specifically the Capacity Market. This communication will be realised through the Knowledge Engine, which will enable integration with the BlueBird Trading Manager component responsible for managing flexibility participation in market mechanisms.

IV.6. BC6 – ENLION Waterworks building with renewable storage

The ENLION business case focuses on integrating a waterworks facility into the BlueBird platform to enable advanced energy management and the utilisation of flexibility services. The objective of this pilot is to optimise the operation of the waterworks infrastructure by considering electricity price signals and locally generated renewable energy, while also evaluating the flexibility potential of the facility.

Within this business case, two control strategies are considered. The first strategy focuses on optimising the operation of the waterworks assets by considering electricity pricing signals and the availability of locally generated energy. In this scenario, the system operates without direct interaction with flexibility trading markets and aims to minimise operational energy costs by exploiting the inherent flexibility of the waterworks infrastructure.

The second strategy aims to determine the flexibility capabilities of the waterworks facility and enable its participation in flexibility markets through the aggregation of multiple building or asset flexibilities. In this case, the flexibility potential identified within the waterworks infrastructure can be aggregated with other assets and offered to the flexibility market through the corresponding BlueBird components.

The expected BlueBird components involved in this business case are presented in the following figure. In the first control strategy, the Trading Manager is not used, as no interaction with the flexibility trading market is required. In the second control strategy, all BlueBird components may be used, enabling interaction with the flexibility market. In situations where flexibility is not traded, the optimisation of the building assets is still performed based on electricity pricing signals.

Figure 24. Expected BlueBird modules deployed in BC6.

IV.6.1. IT structure deployed

The automation system at the waterworks facility is currently being upgraded to support integration with the ENLION platform and the BlueBird services. The waterworks infrastructure includes multiple operational assets, such as pumps, sensors, energy meters, and other equipment required for the facility's operation. These devices are connected to the local automation and supervisory control system, which is responsible for monitoring and managing the operation of the waterworks installation.

To enable communication between the waterworks infrastructure and the ENLION services, an IoT gateway is deployed at the site. This gateway aggregates operational data from the automation system and enables communication with the ENLION servers.

The identification of devices within the waterworks infrastructure follows a standardised industrial naming convention based on recognised ISO guidelines. This approach enables a consistent representation of the connected assets and facilitates the integration of operational data into the ENLION platform and the BlueBird services.

The current ENLION IT architecture includes a real-time data infrastructure consisting of a Kafka cluster connected via MQTT communication, with InfluxDB used as the primary database for storing time-series operational data.

The ENLION Virtual Power Plant (VPP) platform, which is used to monitor and manage distributed energy assets, is based on proprietary automation software. The VPP platform operates within a Docker-based environment that enables scalable deployment and integration of software services.

The overall architecture of the ENLION BC6 pilot, including the interactions among the waterworks infrastructure, the ENLION platform, and the BlueBird services, is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 25. ENLION BC6 system architecture showing the interactions among the waterworks automation system, the ENLION platform, and the BlueBird services.

IV.6.2. Data exchange and system integration

The ENLION data platform serves as the central hub for data exchange among the waterworks infrastructure, the ENLION Virtual Power Plant platform, and the BlueBird services.

Operational data generated by the waterworks assets is collected through the automation system and transmitted to the IoT gateway installed at the site. The gateway aggregates the measurement data and enables communication with the ENLION backend services.

Communication between the local infrastructure and the ENLION platform is performed using the MQTT protocol, allowing efficient transmission of operational data. Within the ENLION backend infrastructure, incoming data streams are handled by the real-time data platform running on the Kafka cluster.

The stored data in the database can then be accessed by the BlueBird services responsible for analysing operational data, performing optimisation processes, and evaluating the flexibility potential. These services can use the available operational and contextual data to support optimisation strategies for the waterworks facility.

In addition to operational data from the waterworks infrastructure, the system can also incorporate external data sources, such as electricity price signals or other contextual information relevant for optimisation processes.

The processed data and analysis results can be visualised through the BlueBird user interface, enabling system operators to monitor system performance and evaluate energy consumption patterns.

The overall IoT data flow implemented in the BC6 pilot is illustrated in the following figure.

Architecture

Figure 26. BC6 actual IoT data flow diagram.

The diagram presents the main data flows between the automation system, the IoT gateway, the ENLION data platform and the BlueBird services used for data processing and optimisation.

IV.7. BC7 – Hotels with PV, biomass-driven CHP and charging stations

IV.7.1. Modules within the BC7 pilot

This business case aims to unlock flexibility from two typical electrical hotel assets. The first is the hotel’s refrigeration compressors used to refrigerate the hotel’s kitchen cold storage facilities, and the second is the EV charging infrastructure provided to the guests in the hotel parking lot.

Both cases aim to reduce costs for the operator, the hotel, by leveraging the flexibility potential through optimised operations to minimise electricity costs based on day-ahead auction prices provided by the Trading Manager. The Flexibility Manager uses this price data, along with information from the digital twins, to schedule optimal operations.

In the cold storage case, the cold storage controllers receive temperature setpoints for each cold storage cell. These controllers are used as an indirect control of the refrigeration compressors. The compressors supply multiple cells. The controllers use the temperature setpoint to control the evaporation fans inside the cells. This reduces the refrigeration liquid’s pressure, activating the pressure-controlled electrical compressors. The cold storage use case relies purely on automatic control.

In the EV charging station case, the charging stations receive optimal charging schedules to follow for each EV charger. This information can be injected into the OCPP feed used by the charging backend to communicate with the individual charging stations and control their operation. Different from the cold storage case, smart charging requires user interaction. This interaction requires another Bluebird module, the User Interaction Tools. Users are required to provide smart charging windows, which define the time window in which the Flexibility Manager can determine the optimal schedule for charging operation. The last module is used for administration during pilot operation to change optimisation parameters during trials or monitor the pilot operation.

EWB hosts the BlueBird services within this BC, with technical support from ENLION (BC6). Therefore, as in BC6, all of this is tied together by an Apache Kafka cluster for streamlined communication and database connectivity, as represented in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Expected Bluebird Modules deployed in BC7.

IV.7.2. IT structure deployed and Asset communication

The infrastructure described above and depicted in Figure 27 will be hosted on an EWH server. However, the structure follows ENLIONS’s IT architecture. Apache Kafka is used as a central data hub, and InfluxDB is serving as the primary database. External assets connect to Kafka via MQTT. The communication between the different Docker containers for the modules on the server is yet undefined.

As described above, to control the electrical refrigeration compressors, individual cold storage cell temperature controllers serve as proxies. These are Carell IR33+ devices. Figure 28 depicts their actuation path. By adding a serial adapter, they can be controlled via Modbus. For this purpose, again, similar to ENLIONS' implementation, an IoT edge device will be deployed. Here, the temperature setpoints provided by the Flexibility Manager through Kafka and MQTT can be translated into the correct controls.

Figure 28. Cold Storage Control communication scheme.

The control of charging stations is usually the role of commercial billing backend providers like Chargecloud. They use the standard OCPP for communication. However, OCPP is a strictly bilateral protocol. To realise this use case, EWH partnered with the service provider Innocharge, which will provide an OCPP proxy. This collaboration allows draining the OCPP feed into the EWH server and injecting the optimised charging profiles later. Figure 29 shows this setup.

Figure 29. Control of Charging Stations via OCPP Proxy.

To realize the use cases, some additional sensors are needed. For these, the LoRaWAN technology is used. Here, EWH partnered with AÜW for sensor configuration and management. The measurements arrive at

AÜW's server, which manages a local LoRaWAN grid, and are then forwarded to the Bluebird infrastructure via MQTT.

Figure 30. LoRaWAN Measurement Setup.

IV.7.3. State of implementation

The server for this business case has been acquired, but the planned architecture is being implemented. The Kafka topics and payloads are in the definition phase to deploy the presented cases on the server.

The LoRaWAN measurements for the refrigeration cells are already operational. The setup of the other two measurement blocks was delayed due to hardware failures. The fixed hardware delivery is scheduled for mid-March 2026. The collected data is currently stored on an AÜW database.

The operation of a single charging station using an Innocharge proxy has been successfully deployed and tested. With the architecture in place, further modules will be tested, including the cold storage, once the hardware failures are solved.

V. CONCLUSION

This document outlines the approach for designing and implementing the data infrastructure developed within the project. It emphasises the data model, ontology alignment, system architecture, and the data harmonisation processes, which are essential for managing complex building-related data.

A key aspect of this approach is the use of a graph-based data model. This model allows the representation of complex relationships among entities, such as patrimony assets, spaces, objects, systems, and devices. By organising information into interconnected nodes and relationships, the model creates a flexible, scalable framework that effectively represents the hierarchical and functional structures of buildings and their associated infrastructures.

The BIGG ontology with the developed extensions is essential for ensuring that the data model adheres to recognised semantic standards. This adherence promotes interoperability, consistency, and integration across various data sources. By utilising established ontologies and standard vocabularies such as SAREF, GeoNames, QUDT, and SSN, the system ensures that data from diverse systems can be integrated and interpreted consistently.

A key component of the platform is the data harmonisation process, which converts raw data into structured information that aligns with the project's data model. Using data pipelines, incoming data is enriched with contextual metadata and integrated into the graph structure. Additionally, other pipelines enable the system to deliver processed data to external services, dashboards, and analytical modules through API-based communication.

Overall, the proposed framework provides a robust, extensible, and interoperable infrastructure for managing building-related data. By combining semantic modelling, graph databases, and harmonised data pipelines, the system supports efficient monitoring, analysis, and decision-making, while ensuring that the platform can be extended and replicated in other contexts or pilot sites in the future.

This document also presents the BlueBird repository, which represents a key element of the project's technical infrastructure. The repository ensures that the code developed within the project is accessible beyond the consortium partners, promoting transparency and facilitating the reuse of the project's results. In addition to serving as a collaborative development space for the project partners, it also provides a practical mechanism for distributing the different software modules required by the pilot sites for deployment and testing.

In line with the project's modular architecture, maintaining an open software approach and providing comprehensive documentation are essential to support replication and reuse beyond the project's scope. By making the components openly available and clearly documented, external organisations can more easily understand, adapt, and implement the solutions developed within BlueBird. This approach strengthens the project's long-term impact by enabling other stakeholders to replicate and extend the platform across different contexts and environments.

Finally, this document also presents the current deployment status of all the BCs, providing an overview of progress at each pilot site in implementing and integrating the BlueBird modules. The analysis shows that development levels vary across pilots and UCs. In some cases, the deployment is already at an advanced stage, while in others, the implementation is still progressing through intermediate steps. These differences are mainly due to the initial conditions and integration maturity of the existing infrastructures at each pilot site, as well as the availability of data sources and the complexity of the local systems that need to be integrated.

Despite differences in starting points and development phases, all pilots are actively progressing toward the common objective of deploying, integrating, and validating the BlueBird modules in their respective environments. The platform's modular architecture facilitates this process by allowing components to be gradually integrated to meet the specific needs and technical constraints of each pilot. As a result, even pilots that began with lower levels of system integration can progressively adopt the required modules and align their infrastructures with the BlueBird framework.

